

Volatile Constituents of *Hypericum elodeoides* Chois

D. K. MATHELA and C. S. MATHELA*

Department of Chemistry, Kumaun University, Nainital-263 002

and

VASU DEV

California State Polytechnic University, Pomona, California-91768

Manuscript received 29 September 1983, revised 23 April 1984, accepted 10 August 1984

The essential oil of *Hypericum elodeoides* Chois (aerial part) has been found to contain nonane, four mono- and eight sesqui-terpene hydrocarbons, two mono- and five sesqui-terpene alcohols, and 7-hydroxycalamenene.

HYPERICUM elodeoides Chois. (Hypericaceae) is a perennial herb growing in tropical Himalayan forest. No work has been reported on the composition of the essential oil of this plant. The *Hypericum* species are frequently used as anthelmintic and as a remedy for dog-bite and bee-sting, and their seeds as diuretic and antispasmodic¹. The present paper describes the characterization of 21 compounds in the essential oil of this species.

Experimental

The plants were collected from Bhowali (Nainital) in the month of September. The essential oil from the aerial part of *H. elodeoides* was extracted by steam distillation using a copper still fitted with spiral condenser and taken in petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). It was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and the essential oil was concentrated by distilling off the solvent under reduced pressure. The physico-chemical properties of the oil were determined by standard methods².

The gas chromatography of the oil was performed on Varian 3700 using stainless steel column (10' x 1/8") packed with 100-120 mesh chromosorb-G HP coated with 5% OV-101. The essential oil was analysed by GC/MS (Finnigan model 4000 GC/MS with data system) using 25 meter fused silica capillary column coated with SE-30. The programming was done from 80 to 200° at 5°/min. Helium was the carrier gas. The ionization energy used in MS was 70 eV under EI conditions. The mass spectra in the GC/MS analysis were recorded corresponding to the GC peaks and percentage area covered by each peak was also determined.

Results and Discussion

The essential oil from the fresh plant material was obtained in 0.1% yield. The physico-chemical properties determined are, specific gravity, 0.9120/20°; ref. index, 1.4856/20°; acid value, 1.02;

ester value, 3.11; ester value after acetylation, 95.24; and carbonyl value as C₁₀H₁₆O, 2.2. The physico-chemical data indicate that the acids, esters and the carbonyl compounds constitute about 6% of the oil. The ester value after acetylation shows high percentage of alcohols in the oil.

TABLE I—CONSTITUENTS OF ESSENTIAL OIL OF *H. elodeoides*

Compound	Content in oil %	M ⁺	m/e (100%)
<i>Hydrocarbons</i>			
Nonane	0.83	128	43
α-Pinene	1.03	136	93
β-Pinene	0.78	136	93
Myrcene	0.56	136	93
Limonene	3.70	136	68
α-Curcumene	2.34	202	119
trans-β-Farnesene	19.21	204	69
allo-Aromadendrene	8.33	204	41
Bergamotene	4.56	204	93
γ-Muurolene	1.71	204	161
Calamenene	1.86	202	159
β-Bisabolene	7.37	204	69
Caryophyllene	3.53	204	41
<i>Alcohols</i>			
α-Terpeniol	0.62	154	59
Lavandulol	0.87	154	69
Elemol	5.26	222	93
Farnesol	5.16	222	69
β-Santalol	0.34	222	93
β-Bisabolol	2.10	220	81
Cedrol	21.38	222	95
Unidentified	2.77	220	60
<i>Phenol</i>			
7-Hydroxycalamenene	0.95	218	175

The mass spectra were identified by comparison of the spectra with those of authentic samples and published results³⁻⁹. One aliphatic hydrocarbon (0.83%), 4 monoterpene hydrocarbons (6.07%), 8 sesquiterpene hydrocarbons (48.96%), 2 monoterpene alcohols (1.49%), 5 sesquiterpene alcohols (34.24%)

and 7-hydroxycalamenene (0.95%) identified in the oil are given in the Table 1.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Mr. A. Greeley, University of California, Irvine for GC/MS of the samples.

References

1. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Periodical Experts, Delhi, 1975, Vol. I, p. 258.
2. E. GÜNTHER, "The Essential Oils", D. Van Nostrand Reinhold and Co., New York, 1949, Vol. I.
3. E. VON SYDOW and R. RYHAGE, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1963, **17**, 2025.
4. Y. MASADA, "Analysis of Essential Oils by Gas Chromatography and Mass Spectrometry", John Wiley, New York, 1976.
5. C. S. MATHELA, "Personal Compilation of Mono- and Sesquiterpenoids".
6. M. G. MOSHONAS and E. D. LUND, *Flavour Ind.*, 1970, **1**, 375.
7. J. ANDERSSON and E. VON SYDOW, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1964, **18**, 1105.
8. E. VON SYDOW, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1963, **17**, 2504.
9. L. H. ZALKOW, J. T. BAXTER, R. J. MCCLURE and M. M. GORDON, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1980, **43**, 598.